

Through Students' and Lecturers' Eyes: Kazakhstani Medical Students' Needs and Self-Efficacy Beliefs in Learning English

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Abstract: English as a lingua franca is crucial in the medical field, enabling access to international research and facilitating communication in diverse healthcare settings. This study aimed to characterize the current state of English language teaching at Kazakhstani medical faculties, evaluate students' needs and self-efficacy in general and medical English, and identify challenges and opportunities for course improvement. A mixed-method approach was used, including syllabus analysis, surveys of lecturers and students from multiple universities, and interviews with both groups. The current state of English language teaching at Kazakhstani medical faculties reveals several challenges and areas for improvement. Key issues include students' difficulty with fluent colloquial speech, limited resources and instructional time, classroom organization difficulties, and inadequate school-level preparation. Evaluating students' needs and self-efficacy beliefs in English for general and medical purposes revealed more substantial confidence in general English skills than in medical-specific communication. Both lecturers and students highlighted speaking skills as a critical area for development. Lecturers also emphasized aligning course content with real-world medical contexts, focusing on medical terminology and professional communication. To address these challenges, expanding instructional hours, modernizing teaching resources, integrating digital tools, and incorporating experiential learning are recommended better to equip medical students for their professional communication needs.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Genel amaçlar için İngilizce
Tıbbi amaçlar için İngilizce
İhtiyaç analizi
Akademik öz yeterlilik

Öğrencilerin ve Öğretim Görevlilerinin Gözünden: Kazakistanlı Tıp Öğrencilerinin İngilizce Öğrenme İhtiyaçları ve Öz Yeterlilik İnançları

Özet: İngilizcenin ortak dil olarak kullanımı, tıp alanında uluslararası araştırmalara erişimi sağlamak ve sağlık hizmeti ortamlarında iletişimi kolaylaştırmak açısından büyük önem taşımaktadır. Bu çalışma, Kazakistan'daki tıp fakültelerinde İngilizce dil eğitiminin mevcut durumunu belirlemeyi, öğrencilerin genel ve tıbbi İngilizce konusundaki ihtiyaçlarını ve öz-yeterliliklerini değerlendirmeyi, derslerin geliştirilmesine yönelik zorlukları ve fırsatları tespit etmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Bu doğrultuda, müfredat analizi, farklı üniversitelerden akademisyenler ve öğrencilerle yapılan anketler ve her iki grupta gerçekleştirilen mülakatları içeren karma yöntem yaklaşımı kullanılmıştır. Kazakistan'daki tıp fakültelerinde İngilizce eğitiminin mevcut durumu, çeşitli zorluklar ve iyileştirilmesi gereken alanlar olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Başlıca sorunlar arasında öğrencilerin akıcı gündelik konuşmada zorlanmaları, sınırlı kaynaklar ve ders saatleri, sınıf içi organizasyon güçlükleri ve okul öncesi hazırlığın yetersizliği yer almaktadır. Öğrencilerin genel ve tıbbi İngilizce konularındaki ihtiyaçları ve öz-yeterlilik inançları değerlendirildiğinde, genel İngilizce becerilerine yönelik özgüvenin, tıbbi terminoloji ve iletişim becerilerine kıyasla daha yüksek olduğu görülmüştür. Hem akademisyenler hem de öğrenciler, konuşma becerilerinin geliştirilmesi gereken en kritik alanlardan biri olduğunu vurgulamıştır. Akademisyenler ayrıca ders içeriklerinin gerçek tıbbi bağlamlarla uyumlu hale getirilmesi, tıbbi terminoloji ve mesleki iletişim üzerine odaklanması gerektiğinin altını çizmiştir. Bu zorlukların üstesinden gelebilmek için ders saatlerinin artırılması, öğretim materyallerinin modernize edilmesi, dijital araçların entegrasyonu ve deneysel öğrenme yöntemlerinin derslere dahil edilmesi önerilmektedir.

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1. Introduction

English is a key tool for national development and globalization in many East Asian countries, particularly in the three most populous nations: China, South Korea, and Japan (Choi, 2021; Rodis & Locsin, 2019). Similarly, Kazakhstan, located at the crossroads of Eastern Europe and Central Asia, also prioritizes English for global integration. The country's language policy designates Kazakh as the state language to strengthen national unity and cultural identity, Russian as a tool for intercultural communication and cooperation with post-Soviet states, and English as the primary language for global economic integration and international business (Tlepbergen *et al.*, 2024).

In the healthcare sector, English proficiency is increasingly regarded as essential, with foreign researchers highlighting its importance for effective communication (Khalili & Tahririan, 2020; Tweedie & Johnson, 2019). Recognizing this, Kazakhstani higher education institutions have prioritized enhancing foreign language education for future healthcare professionals. As part of this effort, all students must complete 10 credits in the Foreign Language course (Order of the Minister of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2022). Kazakhstani universities adopt varied strategies for designing a syllabus for teaching English to medical students, aligning with the state recommendations to use the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) (Order of the Minister of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2018).

Furthermore, recent education policy reforms by the Order of the Minister of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (2022) and the Order of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Kazakhstan (2022) grant universities the autonomy to adjust the content of disciplines such as foreign language, Russian language, information and communication technologies, and physical education within the framework of the standard curricula better to meet the specific needs of their educational programs. These reforms emphasize aligning language instruction with the specific career needs of students, ensuring its relevance to their professional contexts. While there has been some research on the English language needs of medical students in Kazakhstan, such as the study conducted by Kuzembayeva and Zhakanova (2021), which investigated the attitudes, strengths, weaknesses, and language needs of first- and second-year students, our study differs in its scope and methodology. Specifically, we investigate the current state of English language teaching at Kazakhstani medical faculties and explore medical students' needs and self-efficacy in learning general and medical English from the perspectives of both lecturers and students. To do so, the following research questions are addressed:

1. How do lecturers and students at Kazakhstani medical faculties view university-level English courses?
2. What are the characteristics of Kazakhstani medical students' target needs and self-efficacy beliefs in English for General and Medical Purposes?
3. How can the university-level English courses at Kazakhstani medical faculties be improved from the lecturers' and students' viewpoints?

1.1. Literature Review

1.1.1. *English for General and Medical Purposes*

According to the framework presented by Hutchinson and Waters (1987), English language teaching (ELT) is divided into two main branches: English for specific purposes (ESP) and general English (GE). Further expanding on this, Brown (2016) suggests that ESP can be

subdivided into English for academic purposes (EAP) and English for occupational purposes (EOP). EOP, in turn, is categorized into specific sectors such as medical, hotel, construction, and others, depending on the industry focus. The main distinction between teaching GE and ESP is their primary learning goals and expected learning outcomes. The roots of English for medical purposes (EMP) can be traced back to the mid-twentieth century when English became the lingua franca of scientific communication in general and medicine in particular (Salager-Meyer, 2014). EMP has grown significantly by addressing medical students' and professionals' specific language needs (Liu et al., 2023). EMP, as noted by Choi (2021), refers to English language instruction tailored for medical professionals, researchers, and students, helping them develop the language and communication skills needed for careers in healthcare and medicine.

1.1.2. *Target needs analysis (TNA)*

Teaching a second language in the medical field is challenging due to the need to master medical terminology, doctor-patient communication, and cross-cultural skills (Rodis & Locsin, 2019). Unfortunately, despite many efforts, most Kazakhstani school students and graduates do not meet the required levels of English proficiency (Kambatyrova, 2024). That is why university foreign language instructors and students might face unique needs and specific challenges in teaching and learning English. It is of high importance to investigate students' language learning needs. Hutchinson and Waters (1987) defined TNA as an umbrella term that investigates students' language necessities, lacks, and wants. A consortium of researchers has reached a common conclusion: it is essential to conduct an ongoing needs analysis to fully understand students' specific learning and pragmatic needs when designing a course (Choi, 2021; Dunifa, 2023; Hutchinson & Waters, 1987; Kuzembayeva & Zhakanova, 2021; Wang et al., 2024).

1.1.3. *Academic self-efficacy (ASE)*

In 1977, Albert Bandura introduced the concept of self-efficacy, rooted in his social cognitive theory, which refers to an individual's confidence in their ability to perform specific tasks and plays a key role in shaping behavior, motivation, and persistence (Luo et al., 2024; Yusuf, 2011). In education, self-efficacy is called academic self-efficacy (ASE), referring to how confident learners feel about their ability to do well in a specific subject (Hirosawa et al., 2024). Students' self-perceptions of their ability to succeed in specific tasks differ from general beliefs about themselves, as they are closely tied to specific tasks and situations. Although students' self-assessments may not always be fully reliable, research over the past two decades has shown that self-efficacy, or belief in one's abilities, strongly predicts motivation and learning outcomes (Zimmerman, 2000). A study by Wang et al. (2024) on Chinese EFL learners demonstrated that while students expressed high needs for English for general academic purposes (EGAP), their levels of self-efficacy in this area were comparatively low, particularly among those in teaching-oriented universities. Hirosawa et al. (2024) found that fostering a supportive classroom environment that meets students' psychological needs can enhance ASE and perceived competence, as these factors are closely interconnected and crucial for language learning success.

2. Method

2.1. Research Design

The present study is descriptive and employs a mixed-method research design. It incorporates both quantitative and qualitative approaches to achieve data triangulation. A large-scale descriptive study was set up to investigate the process of English language teaching in

Kazakhstani medical faculties and analyze medical students' needs and self-efficacy beliefs in English for general and medical purposes.

2.2. Participants

The online questionnaire study involved 31 lecturer respondents from 5 different universities: 32.26% (10 respondents) were from Asfendiyarov Kazakh National Medical University (KazNMU), 16.13% (5 respondents) were from Al-Farabi Kazakh National University (KazNU), 22.58% (7 respondents) were from Astana Medical University (AMU), 12.90% (4 respondents) were from Semey Medical University (SMU), and 16.13% (5 respondents) were from Marat Ospanov West Kazakhstan Medical University (WKMU). In terms of teaching experience, 19.68% (3 respondents) had 5 years or less of experience, 6.45% (2 respondents) had 6-9 years, 45.16% (14 respondents) had 10-19 years, and 38.71% (12 respondents) had 20 years or more. Lastly, in terms of their positions, 54.48% (17 respondents) were senior lecturers, 41.94% (13 respondents) were lecturers, and 2.23% (1 respondent) were assistant lecturers.

The online questionnaire study of medical students involved 901 student respondents from five different universities in Kazakhstan: 21.98% (198 respondents) from KazNMU, 2.89% (26 respondents) from KazNU, 54.83% (494 respondents) from AMU, 11.54% (104 respondents) from SMU, and 8.77% (79 respondents) from WKMU. The academic year of the students was diverse, with 18.09% (163 respondents) in their first year, 53.72% (484 respondents) in their second year, 15.21% (137 respondents) in their third year, 8.21% (74 respondents) in their fourth year, 4.22% (38 respondents) in their fifth year, and 0.55% (5 respondents) in their sixth year.

Personal interviews were conducted with 11 students and five lecturers using the convenience sampling method. They were from three universities that were easily accessible to us. The profiles of the 11 interviewed students are as follows. Regarding academic year, 18.18% (2 students) were in their first year, 72.73% (8 students) were in their second year, and 9.09% (1 student) were in their third year. The universities represented were KazNMU (18.18%, two students), KazNU (36.36%, four students), and SMU (45.45%, five students). The profiles of the five interviewed lecturers are as follows. Regarding position, 60.00% (3 lecturers) were senior lecturers, and 40.00% (2 lecturers) were lecturers. The participants were from KazNMU (40.00%, two lecturers), KazNU (20.00%, one lecturer), and SMU (40.00%, two lecturers). The sample can be considered representative as it includes students and lecturers from five different universities, various medical programs, and different academic years, capturing a broad range of perspectives. This diversity ensures that the findings reflect the experiences of a broad cross-section of medical students and lecturers in Kazakhstani medical faculties.

2.3. Data Collection

The content analysis of foreign language syllabuses was based on syllabuses collected from universities offering "Medicine" and "General Medicine" programs." The syllabuses were analyzed to identify course titles, academic years and terms, credit allocation, and the departments responsible for teaching foreign language courses. Additionally, we analyzed the content of the syllabuses to determine the proportion of general and medical English topics included in the courses. To supplement this analysis, we communicated with university administrations and foreign language departments to gather additional details and verify the

information. The content analysis of syllabuses was conducted manually using Microsoft Excel.

An online questionnaire survey of lecturers was comprised of 30 questions, including multiple-choice and open-ended items, to obtain comprehensive insights from lecturers. The questionnaire addressed various aspects of medical language education, such as teaching experience, course content, methods, and materials used. It was designed to include quantitative and qualitative questions to capture various opinions and detailed feedback. A literature review on TNA and ASE was conducted to develop the questionnaire. Additionally, questions for this study were adapted from the questionnaire developed by Wang *et al.* (2024) to align with the study's objectives. The questionnaire was designed using Likert-type questions to gather the required information effectively and ensure ease of use for respondents. Specific questions were double-checked to enhance reliability.

A pilot study was carried out to refine the questionnaire, leading to necessary amendments. The questionnaire underwent multiple revisions following the piloting phase to ensure clarity and simplicity. A variety of question types was included to maximize the questionnaire's effectiveness. Initially, it was administered to 10 lecturers and 100 students. However, six respondents (three lecturers and three students) did not complete all the questionnaire sections, and their responses were excluded from the study. During the piloting phase, participants were selected through convenient random sampling and excluded from the primary survey to avoid bias. Their feedback highlighted the need to clarify some terms and address issues like small font size, prompting adjustments to the questionnaire layout. The questionnaire's validity and reliability were assessed, with adjustments made based on the findings. SPSS AMOS 22 was used for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) with a single-factor model applied to all variables to test validity. Some items identified through confirmatory factor analysis with a single factor were removed from the scale to ensure validity. The reliability of the overall scale was measured at 0.82, which is considered highly reliable in social sciences, while the reliability of the subsections exceeded 0.60, confirming the scale's overall reliability.

The online questionnaire survey of students consisted of three parts. The first part was dedicated to respondents' profiles, and information such as age, gender, nationality, university, academic year, educational program, and language of instruction was collected. The second part consisted of whether students studied GE and EMP at university, to what extent they were satisfied by the university-level English courses, and what improvements they might seek. The third part used the TNA and learner academic self-efficacy (LAS) scales. Our TNA scale comprises three subscales: necessities (9 items, e.g., "As a medical student, I need to study English..."), lacks (16 items, e.g., "It is difficult for me to..."), and wants (16 items, e.g., "I hope I will be able to... by studying English at university"). The LAS scale comprises 24 items (e.g., "I can ... in English"). Both scales were scored using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Totally disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree, 5 = Totally Agree).

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore educators' perspectives on teaching English to medical students. The interview guide included 13 questions covering lecturers' demographics, educational background, positions, teaching experience, and views on the importance of English for medical students. It also gathered feedback on students' challenges, resources used in teaching, satisfaction with textbooks, and suggestions for improving foreign language courses for medical students. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gain qualitative insights into students' experiences and perceptions of learning English in a medical faculty context. The interview guide consisted of 11 open-ended

questions covering demographic information, language background, and students' views on the importance and challenges of learning English for medical purposes.

2.4. Data Analysis

The online survey and interviews were initially administered in Kazakh and Russian to accommodate respondents' language preferences. Subsequently, all survey and interview responses were translated into English for analysis and interpretation. The responses were automatically compiled into a Google Forms dataset and then exported to Microsoft Excel and SPSS for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were calculated. Similarly, interviews were conducted in Kazakh and Russian to ensure effective communication. The interview audio recordings were manually transcribed, as the number of participants was small. Participation in the online survey and personal interviews was entirely voluntary, with respondents having the option to withdraw at any time without consequence. The survey ensured anonymity and confidentiality of responses, as no personal identifying information was collected or disclosed. All interview participants provided written informed consent before the interview began. The purpose of the interview and the use of the data were communicated to the participants.

3. Findings

3.1. Content analysis of foreign language syllabuses.

To better understand how universities allocate the 10 credits designated for foreign language courses within the Medicine and General Medicine educational programs, we conducted a comparative analysis of their distribution across academic years, terms, and teaching departments. Information on inaccessible syllabuses was obtained through communication with the administration and language departments. Table 1 summarizes the key findings, highlighting variations in course structure.

Table 1

Foreign language credit distribution (Total = 10 credits)

University	Title of the course/ Year/ Term/ Number of credits (Teaching department)	Course content	
		GE	EMP
A	“Foreign language”/ 1 st year/ 1 st or 2 nd term/ 5 credits (Department of Foreign Languages)	60.00%	40.00%
	“Foreign language”/ 4 th year/ 7 th or 8 th term/ 5 credits (Department of Foreign Languages)	6.67%	93.33%
B	“Foreign language”/ 1 st year/ 1 st or 2 nd term/ 5 credits (Department of Foreign Languages)	100.00%	0.00%
	“English in Medicine”/ 3 rd year, 5 th or 6 th term/ 5 credits (Profiling (Med.) Departments)	The syllabus is not available	
C	“Foreign language”/ 1 st year/ 1 st term/ 5 credits (Department of Foreign Languages)	46.67%	53.33%
	“Foreign language”/ 1 st year, 2 nd term/ 5 credits (Department of Foreign Languages)	53.33%	46.67%
D	“Foreign language”/ 2 nd year/ 3 rd term/ 5 credits (Department of Foreign Languages)	100.00%	0.00%
	“Foreign language”/ 3 rd or 4 th year / 5 credits (Department of Foreign Languages)	The syllabus is not available	

As shown in Table 1, the distribution of 10 credits varies across institutions. Some allocate five credits in the first year and another 5 in the second or third year, while others distribute all 10 credits within the first year—5 in each semester. Later-year courses (e.g., 3rd or 4th year) tend to focus more on EMP, reflecting a shift toward specialized language training. The credit

allocation (5 + 5 credits) remains consistent across the universities listed. Two syllabuses were unavailable, indicating that these courses are either in development or have not been recently updated. Our analysis is based solely on information provided by the universities.

3.2. Online Survey of Lecturers on the Importance of English in Medical Education

Table 2 summarizes the responses from the surveyed lecturers regarding the importance of English for medical graduates and students.

Table 2.

Lecturers' opinions on the importance of English skills for medical graduates and students

Questions	Yes, it is important		No, it is not important		Difficult to answer	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
The importance of English proficiency for medical graduates at a professional level	30	96.77	1	3.23	0	0.00
The significance of studying English for medical purposes for medical students	30	96.77	0	0.00	1	3.23

Table 2 shows that a significant majority of respondents, 96.77% (n = 30), agreed that it is important for a medical graduate to know English professionally. Similarly, when asked about the importance of studying EMP for medical students, 96.77% of respondents (n=30) affirmed its significance. One of the survey questions asked lecturers about the textbooks used to teach English to medical students. Table 3 presents the distribution of textbooks cited by lecturers.

Table 3.

Textbooks used in teaching English in Kazakhstani medical faculties

Textbook title [Translation into English]	The author(s)	Pub. Year	Publisher	f
Учебник английского языка для медицинских вузов [Essential English for medical students]	A.M. Maslova, Z.I. Weinstein, L.S. Plebeian	2018	GEOTAR-media (Russia)	12
Oxford English for Careers: Medicine 1	S. McCarter	2009	Oxford University Press (UK)	6
English in Medicine	E. H. Glendinning & B. Holmström	2005	Cambridge University Press (UK)	2
Английский язык. English in Dentistry [English Language: English in Dentistry]	L. Y. Berzegova	2013	GEOTAR-media (Russia)	3
Английский язык для студентов-стоматологов [English for Dental Students]	V. Mukhina	2002	Higher school (Russia)	3
Check Your English Vocabulary for Medicine: All you need to improve your vocabulary (Check Your Vocabulary)	R. Wyatt	2006	A&C Black (UK)	1
English File	C. Latham-Koenig, C. Oxenden, J. Lambert, P. Seligson	2019	Oxford University Press (UK)	1

Table three suggests that the most frequently mentioned textbook was Essential English for Medical Students by Maslova, Weinstein and Plebeian (2018), with 12 mentions. The second

most frequently cited textbook was Oxford English for Careers: Medicine 1 by McCarter, with six mentions. Additional textbooks are listed in the table. The lecturers mentioned several other textbooks, but we could not identify their full titles or obtain additional information.

To assess the English language proficiency of students entering the university, lecturers were asked to evaluate their levels. The results indicate that most incoming students are at the A1-A2 level (54.84%), followed by a significant portion at the B1-B2 level (41.94%), with only 3.23% achieving C1 proficiency. Additionally, to gain deeper insights into the challenges faced by medical students in foreign language learning, lecturers were surveyed about their observations. Specifically, they were asked to identify which language skill—listening, reading, speaking, or writing—poses the most significant difficulty for students. The results are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4.

Lecturers' observations of medical students' learning difficulties in English courses

Question	Listening n (%)	Reading n (%)	Speaking n (%)	Writing n (%)
According to your observations of students, which of the following causes the most significant difficulty for medical students in foreign language learning?	10 (32.26)	0 (0.00)	18 (58.06)	3 (9.68)

According to the lecturers' observations, speaking was the most significant difficulty for medical students in foreign language learning, with 18 (58.06%) lecturers identifying it as the most challenging skill. Listening was the second most common difficulty, mentioned by 10 lecturers (32.26%). Writing was reported by 3 (9.68%) lecturers as a significant challenge, while reading was not perceived as a major issue, with no lecturers indicating it as a difficulty (0.00%). Additionally, we included an open-ended question (What difficulties do students face in learning in the "Foreign Language" course?) in our survey to give respondents a chance to explain in more detail the challenges students face when learning English. This allowed lecturers to share their experiences and provide a deeper understanding of students' difficulties beyond what closed-ended questions could reveal. To analyze the respondents' answers, we employed a thematic analysis approach. The lecturers reported various language proficiency and skills development issues, particularly in speaking and communication.

A significant challenge identified in English language teaching at Kazakhstani medical faculties is the development of speaking and communication skills. Many lecturers reported that students often experience a fear of speaking in English, which affects their ability to communicate effectively. Difficulties with pronunciation, oral speech, and retelling texts were frequently mentioned, along with students' struggles in using medical terminology appropriately. Additionally, challenges related to grammar and listening skills were highlighted. Example responses: "Problems with pronunciation, fluent colloquial speech"; "Problems with oral speech, retelling of the text."

Resource and time constraints were also identified as significant concerns. Lecturers emphasized the insufficient study hours allocated for English instruction, which limits students' opportunities to practice and improve their language skills. Additionally, lecturers cited a lack of books and methodological literature, implying that students do not have access to enough resources to aid their learning. Another concern was the lack of practical situations where students could apply their English skills. Example response: "Insufficient number of

study hours. There is a lack of practical situations where students must apply a foreign language, such as provision of educational and methodological literature.”

Classroom organization and group dynamics also pose significant difficulties. Large class sizes and the inability to separate students based on their proficiency levels hinder effective language instruction. Overloaded class schedules and the prioritization of specialized courses further complicate the situation. Example responses: “Different levels of English language proficiency, the inability to separate all students by levels due to their large number studying at the department at the same time, insufficient equipment of classrooms, overloaded class schedules and preferences for special subjects”; “Mixing students with different levels of proficiency in the same group.”

Cognitive and motivational factors emerged as additional barriers to student learning. Lecturers observed that many students do not actively engage with the material, often relying on passive learning strategies such as copying content or using AI-based tools like ChatGPT instead of processing information independently. Some students struggle with expressing their thoughts freely, limiting their communication ability. Example responses: “Inability to communicate their thoughts freely”; “The main difficulty is that there is no habit and skill to comprehend the material and perform cognitive work. Students do not memorize new words and material and do not use them as an active dictionary. Some students have a weak ability to choose the appropriate material for the IWS (Independent work of the student) and their presentation of the material - students use ready-made solutions (copy-paste, ChatGPT, etc.), spending a minimum of cognitive effort.” Finally, insufficient school preparation was frequently mentioned as a challenge, particularly for students from rural areas who enter university with a very low level of English proficiency. This poses a significant challenge for lecturers who must help these students improve their language skills, as their weak foundation in English makes it difficult for them to keep up with coursework. Example responses: “low level of knowledge, difficulties in speaking, listening”; “They have a very low level of English proficiency, as most students come from rural areas”; “Weak basic knowledge 70%”

Another open-ended question in the survey sought to uncover lecturers' suggestions for improving English courses for medical students. Respondents proposed various measures to enhance the quality of these courses. These were grouped into several key categories. One of the most frequently mentioned recommendations was increasing instructional hours and expanding course coverage. Many respondents emphasized the need to allocate more hours for foreign language teaching. Suggestions also included making English mandatory for first- and second-year students and increasing opportunities for students to engage with English through structured projects and discussions. Example responses: “To increase the number of hours of foreign language teaching, to increase the involvement of students in practical projects in the specialty, creating real situations for using the language - international internships, communication at conferences, work in projects; “To allocate hours for an IWST (Independent work of the student under the guidance of the teacher).”

Another key recommendation focused on improving classroom resources. Lecturers highlighted the importance of better equipping classrooms to support language learning. Recommendations included providing classrooms with modern textbooks, audio-visual tools, and other technical equipment (e.g., projectors, speakers, and smart boards) and ensuring sufficient books and specialized teaching materials for medical students. Example responses: “Provide the classrooms with books and equipment”; “Technical support (new projectors that can be connected via Bluetooth or USB) for IWS (Independent work of the student) and

classes”; “To purchase a variety of teaching materials for variability in specialties, to provide interactive means of audio visualization of classes (smart boards).” Respondents further emphasized enhancing teaching methods by incorporating diverse and modern approaches such as interactive games and role-playing exercises. Key suggestions included: “Motivate students with active learning methods, including interactive games and discussions”; “Introduce role-playing games to simulate real doctor-patient communication scenarios.”

In addition to methodological improvements, several lecturers highlighted the need to tailor course content to medical students' professional needs. They recommended integrating more medical terminology into the curriculum and developing specialized textbooks and methodological manuals for healthcare students. Example responses: “Introduce more medical terms and develop textbooks focused on medical language.”; “Provide materials that reflect real-life medical communication scenarios.” A recurring theme in the responses was the importance of promoting the practical use of language. Lecturers suggested increasing opportunities for students to practice English in real-world contexts. Example responses: “Create real situations for using the language, such as internships and communication projects.”; “Establish online communication opportunities with foreign students.” Finally, respondents addressed the issue of student motivation and quality control in language learning. Some lecturers proposed measures to motivate students and ensure the quality of their learning. Example responses: “Encourage methods that require cognitive effort, like oral exams instead of written tests.”; “Motivate students by creating opportunities for participation and self-learning.”

3.3. Online Questionnaire Survey of Students at Kazakhstani Medical Faculties

To better understand students' exposure to English language studies, we surveyed their experiences with general English and English for medical purposes at university. The following table presents the distribution of responses regarding their English study background.

Table 5.

Students' responses to English study

Questions	Yes		No		Not sure	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Did you study English for general purposes at university?	741	82.24	87	9.66	73	8.10
Did you study English for medical purposes or professional English at university?	592	65.70	213	23.64	96	10.65

According to Table 5, when asked if they studied English for general purposes at university, 82.24% (741 respondents) answered 'Yes,' 9.66% (87 respondents) answered 'No,' and 8.10% (73 respondents) were 'Not sure.' Regarding English for medical or professional purposes, 65.70% (592 respondents) reported studying it, 23.64% (213 respondents) did not, and 10.65% (96 respondents) were unsure."

Table 6.

Students' perceptions of English language program quality

Question	Answers	n	%
How would you rate the quality of the English language programs offered by your institution?	Excellent	340	37.74
	Good	307	34.07
	Satisfactory	192	21.31
	Unsatisfactory	52	5.77
	Very poor	10	1.11

Table 6 shows that most respondents rated the English language programs positively, with 37.74% rating them as “excellent” and 34.07% as “good”. More than one-fifth of respondents (21.31%) considered the programs “Satisfactory,” while a smaller proportion, 5.77%, rated them as “Unsatisfactory,” and 1.11% rated them as “Very Poor.”

Table 7.

Course improvements from students' viewpoint

Question	Answers	n	%
How do you think the content of the 'Foreign Language' course could be improved?	Pay more attention to listening skills	369	15.56
	Pay more attention to reading skills	243	10.25
	Pay more attention to speaking skills	585	24.67
	Pay more attention to writing skills	212	8.94
	Pay more attention to medical terminology	346	14.59
	Organize English-speaking clubs, workshops, and cultural events to increase the use of the language in social settings	374	15.77
	Supplement course materials with mobile apps designed for language learning	242	10.21

Table seven shows where respondents believe the foreign language course could be improved. The most commonly selected area was speaking skills (24.67%), followed by English-speaking clubs, workshops, and cultural events (15.77%) to increase the use of the language in social settings. Other notable areas for improvement included listening skills (15.56%), medical terminology (14.59%), and reading skills (10.25%). Fewer respondents suggested focusing on writing skills (8.94%) or supplementing the course with mobile apps designed for language learning (10.21%).

3.4. TNA scale (Needs, Lacks, and Wants)

Medical students' perceptions of their English language needs were assessed across various contexts, such as understanding spoken English, engaging with medical and everyday content, and academic communication. The responses, rated on a scale from ‘Strongly disagree’ to ‘Strongly agree,’ are presented in Table 10, showing each statement's mean (M) and standard deviation (SD). Table 8 shows how important medical students think English is for different tasks. The data suggests that medical students overwhelmingly agree that English is essential for their daily and academic activities. Understanding English in medical contexts, such as videos, lectures, and textbooks, is highly important. Students also emphasize the need for English skills to study abroad or participate in internships. The subsequent part of the survey assessed students' perceived difficulties in understanding and using English in everyday and medical-specific contexts (lacks) and expectations for their university-level English courses (wants).

The responses were also rated on a scale from “Strongly disagree” to “Strongly agree,” with the mean (M) and standard deviation (Sd) calculated for each statement to summarize the data. The results are shown in Table 9. Further, to analyze students' needs and areas for improvement, we adapted the Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA) quadrant chart proposed by Lu *et al.* (2023) to better align with the specific context of our study. While the original IPA method categorizes evaluation parameters based on their importance and performance, we modified the chart to focus on two key factors: the X-axis (Lacks), representing students' perceived deficiencies in their English language skills, and the Y-axis (Wants), reflecting their desires and expectations for improvement in these skills (Figure 1).

This adaptation allowed us to assess the gaps and aspirations within students' medical English proficiency more effectively.

Table 8.

TNA scale (needs)

Code	Statements (As a medical student...)	M	SD
N1	I must study English to understand basic spoken English in cafes, shops, and airports.	3.92	1.00
N2	I need to understand videos, presentations, and lectures on medical topics in English.	4.13	0.90
N3	I need to read and understand websites and blogs in English.	4.09	0.88
N4	I need to read and understand medical textbooks and research articles in English.	4.13	0.91
N5	I need sufficient vocabulary to express my opinions on everyday matters in English.	4.20	0.82
N6	I need to make presentations and engage in discussions on medical topics in English.	3.86	0.99
N7	I need to write personal letters or messages in English, as well as non-complex essays and summaries of texts in English.	3.85	0.98
N8	I must write various academic texts in English, such as academic essays, research articles, and literature reviews.	3.73	1.05
N9	I must learn English to study abroad as an exchange student or intern.	4.20	0.91

The quadrant analysis, combined with the data in Table 11, provides a detailed picture of medical students' English language needs (L) and wants (W). Quadrant 1 (High Wants, High Lacks) highlights significant areas requiring immediate attention, particularly in medical English skills, such as understanding lectures (L9), engaging with medical texts (L11, L12), and building professional vocabulary for discussions (L14). These are also reflected in students' top priorities, as shown by their high mean scores for related wants (W9, W11, W12, W14). Quadrant 2 (Low Wants, High Lacks) identifies areas where students struggle, such as writing essays (L8) and delivering oral presentations on medical topics (L13), yet these are less prioritized in their expectations. Quadrant 3 (High Wants, Low Lacks) captures areas where students feel relatively competent but still desire further improvement, such as understanding media content (L2), basic reading skills (L3), and everyday vocabulary (L6). Finally, Quadrant 4 (Low Wants, Low Lacks) includes skills such as basic spoken English in everyday settings (L1, L4) and writing personal messages (L7), where students feel both confident and less motivated to improve.

Figure 1. Quadrant chart: Students' language needs and deficiencies

Table 9.
TNA scale (lacks and wants)

Code	Statements	Lacks (It is difficult for me...)		Wants (I hope I will be able to ... by studying English at university)		Quadrant
		M	SD	M	SD	
		LW1	Understanding basic spoken English in cafes, shops, and airports.	2.66	1.16	
LW2	Understanding TV shows or YouTube videos in English.	2.81	1.14	3.85	0.94	Q3
LW3	Reading and understanding simple texts or emails in English.	2.51	1.13	3.85	0.94	Q3
LW4	Understanding English-language websites and blogs.	2.78	1.12	3.84	0.94	Q4
LW5	Expressing my opinions on everyday matters in English.	2.85	1.17	3.83	0.96	Q4
LW6	Insufficient vocabulary to talk about everyday topics in English.	2.92	1.20	3.87	0.94	Q3
LW7	Writing personal letters or messages in English.	2.87	1.15	3.84	0.94	Q4
LW8	Writing essays or summaries of texts in English.	3.08	1.15	3.84	0.95	Q2
LW9	Understanding presentations or lectures on medical topics in English.	3.03	1.15	3.86	0.95	Q1
LW10	Understanding English-speaking colleagues or patients.	3.05	1.12	3.87	0.94	Q1
LW11	Reading and understanding medical textbooks or research articles in English.	3.11	1.16	3.87	0.94	Q1
LW12	Reading English-language websites and blogs with medicine-related content.	3.08	1.13	3.87	0.93	Q1
LW13	Making oral presentations in English related to medicine in my studies.	3.09	1.15	3.84	0.95	Q2
LW14	Insufficient professional vocabulary to engage in medical discussions in English.	3.35	1.14	3.86	0.94	Q1
LW15	Writing academic essays or summaries of medical texts in English.	3.30	1.12	3.84	0.96	Q2
LW16	Writing medical case reports or complete medical documentation in English.	3.32	1.12	3.85	0.95	Q1

3.5. LAS scale

Table 10 presents medical students' responses to the LAS scale, which assesses their confidence in various aspects of English language proficiency. The data reflects students' perceptions of their abilities to understand and produce English in everyday (GE) and medical contexts (EMP). According to Table 10, the responses from the LAS scale highlight varying levels of confidence among medical students in their English language proficiency. Students displayed the highest confidence in understanding simple phrases and common words about everyday topics (AS1, M = 4.00, SD = 0.94), with over 70% agreeing or strongly agreeing that they could perform this task. Similarly, students expressed confidence in understanding familiar topics like work or hobbies (AS2, M = 3.94, SD = 0.95) and reading short, simple texts to find specific information (AS5, M = 3.86, SD = 0.98). Conversely, areas requiring advanced language skills received lower mean scores, particularly in academic and professional contexts. For example, confidence in writing academic texts such as essays

or literature reviews (AS20) was the lowest ($M = 3.31, SD = 1.12$), with only 40.18% agreeing or strongly agreeing that they could perform this task. Similarly, students reported low confidence in participating in discussions about treatment choices (AS16, $M = 3.37, SD = 1.08$) and explaining health-related issues in conversations with English-speaking patients and colleagues (AS12, $M = 3.38, SD = 1.08$).

Table 10.

LAS scale

Skills	Context	Code	M	SD
Listening	GE	AS1	4.00	0.94
	GE	AS2	3.94	0.95
	EMP	AS3	3.74	0.99
	EMP	AS4	3.48	1.01
Reading	GE	AS5	3.86	0.98
	GE	AS6	3.85	0.99
	EMP	AS7	3.58	1.02
	EMP	AS8	3.41	1.07
	GE	AS9	3.74	1.00
	GE	AS10	3.67	1.03
Speaking	EMP	AS11	3.54	1.05
	EMP	AS12	3.38	1.08
	GE	AS13	3.83	0.97
	GE	AS14	3.66	1.01
	EMP	AS15	3.54	1.03
	EMP	AS16	3.37	1.08
Writing	GE	AS17	3.74	0.99
	GE	AS18	3.58	1.03
	EMP	AS19	3.50	1.03
	EMP	AS20	3.31	1.12
Study skills		AS21	3.61	1.03
		AS22	3.56	1.03
		AS23	3.64	1.00
		AS24	3.68	0.98

3.6. Interviews with Lecturers

Table 11 below presents lecturers' responses to two key questions: the main difficulties students encounter when learning English at university and their suggestions for improving foreign language courses. This table highlights the key challenges students face in learning English at university, with speaking and writing being the most frequently mentioned difficulties. It also summarizes lecturers' suggestions for improving foreign language courses, emphasizing the need for more interactive opportunities, extended course duration, and a stronger focus on aligning course content with students' future professional needs.

Table 11.

Challenges and improvements.

Question	Results & Examples
What difficulties do students most often face when learning English at university? (listening, reading, speaking, or writing)	Students face several challenges when learning English at university. The most common difficulty is speaking (as mentioned by five lecturers). Writing (mentioned by three lecturers) is another major challenge, mainly because of grammar issues and limited foundational skills. Listening (mentioned by one lecturer) can also be difficult, especially for students with weaker English backgrounds. Representative examples: "...in terms of speech, it is difficult for these people, first, and second. . .there are also difficulties in terms of the writing", "...speaking skills because we have much different

<i>Table continues</i>	
	terminology...”, "...the majority of our students are students with A2 level...as you know, for a person with A2 level, everything is difficult...they understand what they hear but it is difficult for them to speak...”, "...first, it is speaking what they find difficult and second ... writing is also difficult”, "...the main problem is their listening and grammatical errors, this is writing ... it is all because they have a weak school base”.
How do you think the content of a foreign language course can be improved?	Lecturers suggested improving the course by inviting native lecturers, creating debate clubs, and increasing teaching hours, as three hours per week is insufficient. Representative examples: “...invite native lecturers and create a debate club...”, “...number of hours ... we have classes once a week, that is, for three hours... it seems to me that this is not enough”, “...increase the duration...for example, let us say in the first year, then the third year and then the fifth year...”, “...allocate more hours for our course, because it is not just learning medical English, but we need to improve their conversational skills more...”, “...find the connection between...what students need when they graduate from university and what they are studying...”

3.7. Interviews with students

Interviews were conducted to gain deeper insights into students' challenges while learning English at university. This qualitative approach allowed us to explore their experiences and perspectives in greater detail, complementing the quantitative data from the survey.

Table 12.

Challenges faced by students in learning English at university

Question	Results & Examples
What challenges have you encountered while learning English at university? (listening, reading, talking or writing)	Most student interviewees identified speaking as the most challenging aspect of learning English at university, with nine students highlighting this difficulty. A lack of practice was also frequently mentioned, noted by four students, while one pointed to grammar challenges. Representative examples: “very difficult to conduct speaking... regularly... difficult to find a suitable person for that...”, “...most often, this is probably speaking skills, due to the lack of qualified specialists and little practice”, “...for me, probably the most difficult thing is that there is very little practice...”, “...I think nowadays everybody has difficulties in the speaking aspect because we do not have so much practice and when we were in school we just learned the rules, not much practice, ... we were given memorization exercises...so we just memorized...”, “...since I did not pay much attention to English during school ... at university I have difficulties... when retelling large texts...”, “...I think it is mostly speaking because we understand the questions, but it is hard to answer and express our thoughts...”

Table 12 presents students' most common difficulties in learning English at university, as identified in the interviews. As shown in the table, speaking skills emerged as the most significant difficulty for most students, with additional concerns about limited practice opportunities and grammar issues.

4. Discussions

4.1. Discussions on Research Question 1

The findings reveal a near-unanimous agreement among educators on the importance of English proficiency for medical graduates (Table 2). An overwhelming 96.77% emphasized the necessity of mastering English at a professional level and studying English for Medical Purposes (EMP). This consensus highlights the critical role of English in medical students'

academic and professional success, aligning with global trends in medical education where English functions as a lingua franca.

From the student's perspective, the majority expressed positive views regarding the quality of English language programs at their institutions (Table 6). Specifically, 37.74% rated the programs as "Excellent" and 34.07% as "Good". However, 21.31% considered the programs merely "Satisfactory." In comparison, 5.77% rated them as "Unsatisfactory" and 1.11% as "Very Poor." A study conducted by Kuzembayeva and Zhakanova (2021) also highlights students' generally positive perceptions of English language courses within university programs. According to their findings, 30.77% of respondents rated the courses as "Very Effective" and 57.69% as "Effective," with no participants deeming the courses "Not Effective at All." While these results underscore the perceived usefulness of the courses, it is noteworthy that 11.54% considered them only "Somehow Effective." While the overall perception is positive, these findings underscore the need for targeted improvements to enhance program quality and address the concerns of students with less positive experiences.

The survey and interview results highlight speaking as the most challenging skill for students learning English at university (Table 4). According to the survey, lecturers identified speaking ($n = 18$) as the most difficult skill, which the interview participants echoed. The majority ($n = 5$) also singled out speaking as the most challenging skill. When comparing the challenges of listening and writing, differences emerged between the survey and interview responses. In the online survey of lecturers (Table 4), listening was identified as the second most challenging skill ($n = 10$), while only three respondents mentioned writing. In contrast, lecturer interviews revealed that writing ($n = 3$) was considered a significant difficulty by some participants, alongside speaking, while listening was mentioned less frequently ($n = 1$). This variation suggests that the perceived challenges may depend on the data collection method, with surveys capturing broader trends and interviews providing more specific, nuanced insights into the difficulties lecturers and students face.

The interviews with students further emphasized the lack of real-life communication practice as a primary factor in their speaking difficulties. Many students reported having few opportunities to practice speaking English, limiting their ability to develop fluency and confidence. Additionally, some students attributed their challenges to focusing on memorization during their school years rather than on practical application. Addressing these issues through more interactive and communicative learning approaches could help students improve their speaking skills and overcome these challenges in their academic and professional journeys.

4.2. Discussions on Research Question 2

In this study, we explored medical students' needs and self-confidence regarding their English language skills. The results show that students want to improve their general and medical English. They primarily focus on expanding their medical vocabulary, understanding medical content, and studying abroad. First, we found that students feel confident when using English in everyday situations, like understanding basic phrases and having simple conversations. However, they feel less confident about more complex medical topics. Students also strongly desired to improve their medical English skills, particularly in areas like reading medical texts, understanding medical lectures, and communicating with patients and colleagues. They want to be able to talk about medical topics in English clearly and effectively. The findings suggest that while students are motivated to learn English, they need more focused training on medical vocabulary and communication skills. Khalili and Tahririan

(2020) also identified significant challenges in listening and speaking skills, noting that students' proficiency in these areas did not improve during the ESP programs. This finding aligns with our study, reinforcing the critical need for more attention to listening and speaking in medical English education. To better understand students' needs and areas for improvement, we created a quadrant chart (Figure 1) based on two key factors: lacks and wants (Table 9). This chart allowed us to visually categorize the different aspects of language skills according to how students feel about their proficiency and their need for improvement. By analyzing the chart, we can identify key areas that require attention and provide targeted recommendations for intervention.

Q1. High Wants and High Lacks (Top-right quadrant) suggest that these areas require immediate attention, as students want and need improvement in these skills (LW9, LW10, LW11, LW12, LW14, LW16). For instance, LW9 represents difficulty understanding medical presentations or lectures (L9: $M = 3.03$, $SD = 1.15$) and a strong desire to improve in this area (W9: $M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.95$). Focused intervention in these areas may be most beneficial. Q2. Low Wants and High Lacks (Bottom-right quadrant) suggest students need improvement in these areas but do not prioritize them (LW8, LW13, LW15). For example, LW8 corresponds to difficulty writing essays or summaries of texts (L8: $M = 3.08$, $SD = 1.15$) paired with a lower desire for improvement (W8: $M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.95$). Efforts could focus on making these skills more engaging or demonstrating their relevance to students' academic or professional goals. Q3. High Wants, Low Lacks (Bottom-left quadrant) indicates that students desire further improvement in skills they already feel relatively proficient in (LW2, LW3, LW6). For instance, LW2 relates to understanding TV shows or YouTube videos (L2: $M = 2.81$, $SD = 1.14$) paired with a strong desire to enhance this ability (W2: $M = 3.85$, $SD = 0.94$). Providing advanced or supplementary training in these areas could help satisfy students' aspirations for growth. Offering advanced or supplementary training could be valuable here. Q4. Low Wants and low Lacks (Top-left quadrant) likely indicate already well-developed skills, and students do not feel the need for further improvement (LW1, LW4, LW5, LW7). For instance, LW1 corresponds to basic spoken English comprehension in everyday settings (L1: $M = 2.66$, $SD = 1.16$) and a low desire to focus on this skill (W1: $M = 3.84$, $SD = 0.95$). These areas can be deprioritized unless specific feedback indicates otherwise.

4.3. Discussions on Research Question 3

The survey and interview findings provide valuable insights into improving the 'Foreign Language' course for medical students. Lecturers recurrently suggested increasing instructional hours, highlighting the insufficiency of the current schedule. They also recommended expanding the course to include mandatory instruction for first—and second-year students and introducing additional teaching opportunities in the third and fifth years to provide consistent language support throughout the degree. Classroom resources were another critical area identified for improvement. Lecturers stressed the need for modern equipment, such as smartboards, projectors, and audio-visual tools, alongside updated textbooks and teaching materials tailored to medical contexts. Lastly, lecturers proposed creating opportunities for students to practice English in real-world or simulated environments through international internships, projects, debate clubs, and workshops.

The student survey findings supported these recommendations, identifying speaking skills as the top priority for improvement, followed by listening skills and medical terminology. Students also expressed interest in extracurricular activities, such as English-speaking clubs

and workshops, to practice the language in social and professional contexts. While reading and writing were considered less critical, they were still noted as areas requiring attention. Lecturer interviews further reinforced these perspectives, with respondents highlighting the need to align course content with the real-world requirements of healthcare professionals. For example, lecturers suggested linking what students learn during their studies to the practical skills they need in their future careers. To address these issues, the course could be improved by increasing teaching hours to allow more time for skill development, updating classroom resources with modern tools and materials, and using interactive teaching methods like role-plays and group discussions. Focusing on medical communication and integrating real-world practice, such as internships, international collaborations, and workshops, would give students practical experience and confidence in using English. By focusing on these areas, the course can better equip medical students with the language skills necessary to meet the demands of their academic and professional environments.

5. Conclusion

The findings of this study highlight the critical role of English proficiency in medical education at Kazakhstani universities and underscore the need for targeted improvements to university-level English courses. Both lecturers and students recognize the importance of English for academic and professional success, with a shared emphasis on enhancing speaking and listening skills as key priorities. While students generally view the existing programs positively, a significant proportion identified areas for improvement, reflecting the need to address diverse student needs effectively. Students' target needs and self-efficacy beliefs reveal a strong desire to improve general and medical English, focusing on expanding professional vocabulary and mastering medical-specific communication. The quadrant analysis further emphasizes the urgency of addressing areas where students exhibit high needs and motivation for improvement, such as understanding medical lectures, engaging in professional discussions, and reading specialized texts.

Recommendations to improve the 'Foreign Language' course include increasing instructional hours, modernizing resources, and integrating digital tools. Incorporating interactive teaching methods like role-playing, simulations, and extracurricular activities like English-speaking clubs would foster practical language use in professional contexts. Tailoring course content to align with real-world medical scenarios and emphasizing medical terminology will better equip students to meet the demands of their future careers. By implementing these improvements, Kazakhstani medical faculties can provide more effective and relevant language training, empowering students to excel in an increasingly globalized medical environment. Our study may benefit educational administrators and English language educators in medical faculties. It provides actionable insights into students' and lecturers' needs and priorities and highlights the critical importance of aligning English language courses with professional and academic requirements in the medical field.

While this study provides valuable insights into English language education for medical students, it does have certain limitations. The research primarily focuses on immediate perceptions and outcomes, which restricts the ability to evaluate how the skills acquired during the course translate into long-term effectiveness in real-world medical practice. Additionally, lecturer responses may reflect their personal experiences and attitudes toward the curriculum and teaching methods, potentially introducing bias in identifying areas for improvement. Addressing these limitations in future research could help create a more comprehensive understanding of how to enhance English proficiency for medical purposes.

To better understand how to improve English proficiency for medical purposes, future research should address several important areas. First, longitudinal studies are needed to evaluate the long-term impact of interventions such as integrating medical simulations and role-playing into language courses, assessing their effect on students' skills and confidence. Second, exploring the effectiveness of digital tools and mobile apps specifically tailored to medical English education can provide insights into how these technologies enhance learning outcomes. Additionally, investigating the perspectives of practicing healthcare professionals who have completed similar courses will help determine how well their language training prepares them for real-world medical communication. Finally, examining the impact of innovative teaching strategies, such as video-based assignments or blended learning models, on students' language development and confidence in medical communication will offer further insights. By addressing these aspects, future studies can contribute significantly to designing more effective and practical English language education for medical students.

Ethical Issues

The authors declare that this study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country, as participation was voluntary. Written consent was obtained from all participants. Additionally, university administrations granted permission to analyze their syllabuses and distribute survey links to their students and lecturers. The university administrations provided the syllabuses analyzed in this study for research purposes. Per the administrations' agreements, we cannot disclose any part of the syllabuses' content. All data from the syllabuses have been aggregated and anonymized to maintain confidentiality and respect institutional policies. (Date of Confirmation: 04/12/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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